

Detecting Markers of Intelligent Life In Habitable-Zone Earth-like Planets Orbiting White Dwarfs

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ABSTRACT

The possibility of not being alone in the Universe and of finding another form of civilization has always been an interesting and controversial topic. In this paper we are developing a model for the detection of intelligent life-markers on Earth-like planets transiting white dwarfs, by analyzing their atmospheres. It has already been noted that white dwarfs have long-lived habitable zones that may be hosting planets (3 Gyr), which is why we are pointing towards them as a potential source for the future discovery of other intelligent civilizations. The way we are testing whether or not these planets are strong candidates for hosting intelligent life is by analyzing their atmospheric transmission. By performing simulations of the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) spectroscopic observation of an Earth-like planet transiting a white dwarf star, and further focusing our results in the Near-Infrared part of the spectrum, we can check for the molecules present in the atmosphere of the planet. We are particularly looking for given molecules that we know to be produced by artificial means (such as industrial pollution) in the Earths atmosphere. We are reasoning our results on the basis that if we are able to detect these molecules in the atmosphere of Earth-like planets orbiting white dwarfs, then there must be some form of civilization on these planets, which is producing the elements we are looking for.

1. INTRODUCTION

The search for extrasolar planets has increased significantly in the past years with the launch of missions such as NASA's Kepler initiative, which has detected more than 3,500 planetary candidates as of November 2013. There are several ways of detecting the presence of exoplanets the transit method being one of them. Observing a planet while it passes in front of its host star can give valuable information about the physical properties of that planet one can learn about the way the planet has formed, check for the chemical elements present in the atmosphere of the planet, and even hypothesize about its future evolution. This information is meaningful, but hard to obtain with the currently available technological resources.

While the transit method has been used in the past, it has been challenging for astronomers to conduct successful observations of extrasolar planets by using this technique. Given the enormous difference in size between a planet and its host star, the contrast between the light coming from the host star through the atmosphere of the planet, and the light coming directly from the background star is very small: 10^{-3} - 10^{-4} (Loeb, A. Maoz, D 2013). Therefore, it becomes particularly hard to notice the planet during its transit in front of the star. Previous successful results were obtained due to the stability of the Hubble Space Telescope, or because of the closeness of the host star to our Solar System (and implicitly easiness to conduct observations). We are expecting to obtain more successful results with this method in the following years, with the launch of the James Webb Space Telescope. Because of the improved observing resolution of JWST, planetary transits will be easier to observe in the future.

We note that even with better resolution possibilities, observing planetary transits can still be challenging. The relative difference in size between an Earth-like planet and a Sun-like star results in a small contrast during the time of the transit. However, if we focus our observations on smaller stars, the ratio of the size of the planet relative to the size of the host star increases, and therefore we obtain better results. In this paper, we are focusing our calculations on Earth-like planets orbiting around white dwarfs. The relatively small size of the white dwarf ($R_{wd} = 8,500km$ – Suh and Mathews 2000) contributes positively to increasing the contrast between the light coming from the star through the atmosphere of the planet, and the light coming directly from the background star.

In this paper we are focusing on transits of Earth-like planets orbiting around white dwarfs. By obtaining the atmospheric transmission spectrum of these planets we can further check for the molecules present in their atmospheres. Previous papers have already simulated the JWST spectroscopic observations for this scenario, and tested for the presence of bio-markers, mainly for the O₂ absorption bands (Loeb, A. & Maoz, D 2013). Following the model of this paper, we are conducting similar calculations in order to check for markers of intelligent life. The molecules whose spectra we are simulating have been observed in Earth's atmosphere, and they have been recorded as produced by human industrial activity here on Earth. A sample table of the molecules we are focusing on is included below (Table 1).

We perform our calculations on Earth-like planets transiting WDs not only because WDs have a smaller surface area than Main Sequence stars (and therefore higher contrast of the planets atmospheric transmission spectrum over the stellar background), but also because we have learned from previous papers that white dwarfs have long lived habitable zones, which may be hosting planets. It has been estimated that the habitable zone around white dwarfs can be lived for at least 3 Gyr (Agol, 2011). Previous results pointed out the

relatively high probability of finding planets in these long-lived habitable zones. Sion et al.(2009) estimated that 15% of WDs may be hosting terrestrial planets or asteroids, while Zuckerman et al.(2010) estimated the same number to be 30%. Their research methods are similar to one another Sion et al.(2011) showed that at least 15% of the WDs found within 20 parsecs of the Sun have photospheric metals which might originate from accretion of debris disks around them. This further suggests that the same percentage of stars can host planets or asteroid-type bodies. Zuckerman et al.(2010) estimated this number to 30% and supported their results through an analysis of the atmospheric pollution due to chemical elements heavier than Helium.

The above estimates are favorable for our calculations. While there are no observed planets around WDs to date, their existence has been anticipated in Agol (2011) - he switches the search for habitable Earth-like planets from being focused on nuclear burning stars to cool white dwarfs. The habitability of the zones surrounding WDs has also been explored more recently in Kilic et al (2013), who suggest surveying a sample of 10,000 WDs with the Kepler spacecraft, estimating to find up to 100 planets in the WDs habitable zone in a given observing time of 200 days. Even though WDs are stars found in later stages of stellar evolution, planets can still exist around them Silvotti et al. (2007) conclude that planets with orbital distances of less than 2 AU can survive the red giant expansion of their parent stars, and further orbit the star, which can now be found in a post-red-giant phase. Charpinet et al. (2011) also note that planets can survive the engulfment of the envelope of their red giant parent.

Given the high contrast of the planets atmospheric transmission spectrum over the light from the background star, and the possibility of finding planets in the long-lived habitable zone of white dwarfs, we continue our calculations and try to estimate the parameters of our WD sample. We further simulate the atmospheric transmission spectrum

Table 1.

Name of Molecule	Wavelength
SF6	10-11 um
CFC11	8-13 um
CFC12	8-12 um
CFC13	8-14 um
CFC14	6-8 um
HCFC21	11-13 um
HCFC22	7-13 um
CFC113	8-13 um
CFC114	7-12 um
CFC115	7-11 um
CCl4	12-14 um
CH3Cl	3-15 um
COF2	5-14 um
HF	2-3 um
HCl	2-3 um
HBr	1.9-2.0 um

Note. — Molecules we look for.

of an Earth-like planet transiting a WD whose properties are defined accordingly to our sample, and conclude by analyzing whether or not the previously defined list of artificially created molecules can be detected with JWST.

2. WHITE DWARF SAMPLE REQUIREMENTS

We need to estimate the characteristics of a WD sample that through surveying will allow us to observe one Earth-like planet that can be a good candidate for the detection of intelligent life.

Since previous calculations have already been conducted in the field, but for the characterization of a WD sample that allows us to detect bio-markers in general, not markers of intelligent life, the values we estimate for the size and type of the WDs will be the same. We are focusing on the same category of stars and we are using the same technique, the only difference will be in the molecules that we are planning to observe. Therefore, we include below the values corresponding to our sample, as noted in Loeb, A & Maoz, D (2013).

Most of the WDs have a mass of $M_{wd} \sim 0.6M_{\odot}$ (Kepler et al. 2007; Gianninas et al. 2013), or $M_{wd} \sim 0.65M_{\odot}$ (Holberg et al. 2008; Gianninas et al.2011; Falcon et al. 2012; Giammichele et al. 2012). In both of these situations, the corresponding radius of the WD is $R_{wd} \sim 8,500$ km (Suh & Mathews 2000).

Their habitable zone spans from a ≈ 0.005 AU to a ≈ 0.02 AU, and if we accept an average value of $a = 0.01$ AU we can further calculate for the probability of a transit due to a planet of radius R_p :

$$P_{transit} = \frac{R_p + R_{wd}}{a} \tag{1}$$

This results in a value of $P_{transit} = 0.01$, if we accept $R_p = 6,400$ km. Loeb, A. and

Maoz, D. (2013) assume for a 20% proportion of the observed WD sample to have an Earth-like planet orbiting around them. This means that we have to observe at least 500 WDs in order to find one Earth-like planet.

3. REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DETECTION OF INTELLIGENT-LIFE MARKERS

We begin our analysis with a description of the scenario we are going to test for. We must understand under what conditions the transit occurs, in order to further conclude for the requirements for the detection of the molecules we are pursuing.

The key element for understanding the scenario of the transits we are referring to is that when the planet passes in front of the star, the light we observe from the transiting system comes in part through the atmosphere of the planet, in part directly from the background star. When we test for the existence of the molecules listed in Table 1 (above), we look at the light passing through the atmosphere of the planet. However, the resulting information is data affected by noise coming from the star in the background. In order to understand the S/N ratio for our scenario (which will help us decide on the requirements for the detection we are pursuing), we need to evaluate the ratio of the section area of the atmosphere of the planet and the section area of the unocculted background star:

$$\frac{S}{B} = \frac{S_{atm}}{S_{backgroundstar}} \quad (2)$$

Since the planet and the star that we are observing are comparable in size, the section area of the WD that will get covered during the planetary transit will be about one half of the initial section area. The exact occulted value can be obtained by estimating the numerical value of $\frac{2\pi R_p nH}{3}$, where H is the exponential scale height of the planets atmosphere, and nH

is the height above the planets surface at which a line of sight tangent to the planet passes a column of atmosphere equal to one vertical column (Loeb, A. & Maoz, D 2013). The value of n was estimated to $n = 4.2$ by Beckwith (2008), for the case of Earth-like planets. Given this value, and keeping in mind that approximately half of the section area of the WD gets occulted during the transit, we can solve for the ratio S/B, which helps us further calculate the S/N ratio.

$$\frac{S}{B} \approx \frac{4nHR_p}{3R_{wd}^2} \approx \frac{1}{170} (\text{Loeb, A. \& Maoz, D - 2013}) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{S}{\sqrt{170S}} = \frac{S}{N} \quad (4)$$

We note that the values obtained from the above equations are both higher than in the case of transiting systems involving Main-Sequence stars. For the purposes of our paper, we will assume that a given molecule is visible once its $\frac{S}{N} \geq 5$.

It is therefore left to check for each of our molecules if their corresponding $\frac{S}{N} \geq 5$. We analyze individual resolution elements of 10\AA (resolution of JWST) and draw our conclusions.

4. SPECTRAL SIMULATION

We analyze the planetary atmospheric transition at two different levels above the surface of the planet: 17.000 and 45.000 km. Our simulations are focused on the near-mid IR part of the spectrum, between 0.58825 and 33.3333 μm .

The corresponding plots for this wavelength interval are found below.

While the data above looks reasonable, for the interval 2 – 33 um we obtain data that is significantly affected by noise, at both 17 km and 45 km above the surface of the planet. This is summarized in the pictures below:

We also notice that it is difficult to observe each molecule independently – the level of noise becomes increasingly high, covering the spectral lines of the molecule we are trying to resolve:

The above results are reasonable, given that the spectral features of the molecules we are looking for are weak, especially by comparison with other features of more abundant species. It is therefore difficult to pick up a strong signal in these conditions.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We need to check for a sample of ~ 500 WD in order to find one Earth – like planet that may host another form of intelligent–life. The transiting system WD - Earth–like planet is a stable one, with favorable conditions for the development of life. We verify the existence of another civilization by searching for molecules that we know to be produced artificially here on Earth. We simulate atmospheric transmission spectra for these molecules and we further conclude that the signal coming from each one of them individually is weak, particularly if we compare it with the spectral features of more abundant species. We conclude that it is difficult to pick up a strong signal in these conditions. We suggest that for future calculations there should be defined an optimal integration time such that one looks for a given threshold of the concentrations needed in the exoplanet atmosphere to be able to detect one molecule.

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